
Fairly Toolset

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FAIRLY PACKAGE

1	Open Science Festival	1
1.1	1. Activate Organization Account	1
1.2	2. Access Remote Desktop	2
2	Installation	5
2.1	Installing the Toolset	5
2.2	Installing Python Package Only	6
3	Using the JupyterLab Extension	7
3.1	Start JupyterLab	7
3.2	Part 1: Cloning Datasets	8
3.3	Part 2: Create a Fairly Dataset	12
3.4	Part 3: Upload Dataset to Repository	16
3.5	Part 4: Pushing Changes to Data Repository	19
4	Using the CLI	23
4.1	Cloning a Dataset	24
4.2	Creating a Local fairly Dataset	24
4.3	Upload Dataset to Data Repository	26
5	Using the Python API	29
5.1	Cloning a dataset	29
5.2	Creating a local dataset	30
5.3	Uploading a dataset	31
5.4	Pushing changes to a data repository	31
6	fairly	33
6.1	fairly package	33
7	Indices and tables	61
	Python Module Index	63
	Index	65

OPEN SCIENCE FESTIVAL

This page contains information relevant to the **workshop part of the Open Science Festival 2023, Rotterdam.**

Important: If you have received an invitation to join our Virtual Lab. Follow the steps below to configure access to a remote desktop where you can run *Fairly* and its JupyterLab extension during the workshop. This is a convenient way to follow the workshop without installing the toolset on your computer.

Alternatively, you can install the toolset on your computer. See the instructions in installation.

You will receive two emails when you have been added to the Azure Virtual Lab. The first email will contain an invitation to get access to an account in our organisation and a *username*; the second email will contain a *password*. Follow the steps below to configure access to our organisation and the Virtual Lab.

Warning: The invitations will expire after a few days. You will need to contact us to get a new invitation. Please notice that the use of Virtual Labs is still in an **experimental phase** in our organisation, and the invitations will be rolled out gradually up until the date of the workshop. If you have questions or encounter any problems, please contact us via [this email](#).

1.1 1. Activate Organization Account

1. Accept the invitation by clicking the link in the email. You will be redirected to a Microsoft log-in page where you can activate your account
2. Using the *username* and *password* you have received by email activate you account. You must change your password and complete the two-factor authentication using the Microsoft Authenticator app on your phone. **Please make sure to write down your new password.** You will need it to access the Virtual Lab.
3. Once you complete the account activation, log in to the Virtual Lab website <https://labs.azure.com/> using your new account.

Note: If you use other Microsoft accounts, you may need to log out first and then log in again using your new account. Ensure you are logged in to the correct account by checking the account name in the top right corner of the Azure Lab Portal. The account name you will receive from us contains the word **tudeftcloud4researchacc**.

4. You should see the **OpenScience Festival** virtual machine. **Showing the virtual machine in your account may take some time.** Please check after a while if you do not see it immediately.

1.2 2. Access Remote Desktop

On the day of the workshop, you can access the virtual machine using a remote desktop. Follow the steps below to access the remote desktop.

1. Start the virtual machine by switching the toggle button to the left (1). The button will turn blue when the virtual machine is running.

2. Click on the **Connect** button (2). A file with the extension **OpenScienceFestival.rdp** will be downloaded to your computer.
3. On your computer, double-click on the downloaded file. You will be asked to connect to your virtual machine using a username and password. **The username and password for this step will be provided also by email.**

INSTALLATION

The *Fairly Toolset* provides functionality for the core tasks of preparing, uploading and downloading datasets from research data repositories. The toolset currently provides integration with data repositories based on [Zenodo](#) and [Figshare](#).

What's Included:

- fairly Python package
- Command Line Interface (CLI)
- JupyterLab extension

Requirements:

- Python 3.8 or higher
- pip 20.0 or higher
- ruamel.yaml 0.17.26 or higher
- JupyterLablab 3.x

2.1 Installing the Toolset

You can install the full toolset by installing the JupyterLab extension from PyPI. The fairly package and CLI will be installed automatically.

2.1.1 Linux / MacOS

Install the toolset using *pip*

```
pip install jupyter-fairly
```

2.1.2 Windows

1. Download the ZIP file with the [latest release](#) of the JupyterLab extension to a directory.
2. Unzip the content.
3. Using the **terminal**, go to the directory where the ZIP file is located and then to the *jupyter_fairly* sub-directory.
4. Type and run the following command. You need to add Python to the system PATH for this to work.

```
python -m pip install .
```

Warning: For the above to work, you need Python in the PATH environment variable on Windows. If you're not sure that is the case, open the Shell, and type `python --version`. You should see the version of Python on the screen. If you see otherwise, follow these steps to [add Python to the PATH on Windows](#)

2.2 Installing Python Package Only

If all you need is the *fairly* Python package and the CLI, you can install them as following.

2.2.1 Linux / MacOS

On the terminal type:

```
pip install fairly
```

2.2.2 Installing from Source

Installing *fairly* from source requires *setuptools* version 49.0 or later and *pip*.

1. Clone or download the [source code](#):

```
git clone https://github.com/ITC-CRIB/fairly.git
```

2. Unzip if necessary, and go to the *fairly* directory:

```
cd fairly/
```

3. Install the package:

```
pip install .
```

Important: Currently, the toolset only supports data repositories based on [Zenodo](#) and [Figshare](#). For examples on how to use the toolset, read the [Tutorials](#)

USING THE JUPYTERLAB EXTENSION

This tutorial shows how to use the JupyterLab extension to clone and create research datasets using the graphical interface of JupyterLab, and how to upload dataset to popular research data repositories.

If you haven't done so, install the full toolset.

3.1 Start JupyterLab

Start JupyterLab with the **jupyter-fairly** extension. This will start JupyterLab in your browser.

3.1.1 Windows

You will use the Shell Terminal to start JupyterLab.

Important: For the following to work, you need Python in the PATH environment variable on Windows. If you are not sure that is the case, open the Shell, and type `python --version`. You should see the version of Python on the screen. If you see otherwise, follow these steps to [add Python to the PATH on Windows](#)

On the shell type the following and press *Enter*:

```
jupyter lab
```

3.1.2 Linux / MacOS

From the terminal, run:

```
jupyter lab
```

JupyterLab should automatically start on your browser.

3.2 Part 1: Cloning Datasets

Public research datasets can be cloned (copy and downloaded) directly to an empty directory, using the dataset's **URL** or **DOI**. We will use [this dataset](#) from 4TU.ResearchData as an example.

These are other datasets that you can try:

- <https://zenodo.org/record/4302600>
- <https://zenodo.org/record/8273524>

Using the JupyterLab interface, create a new directory called `workshop`. Notice that the content of your main directory would be different.

1. Inside the workshop directory, create a new directory called clone
2. Right click on the left panel to open the context menu
3. Click on *Clone Dataset*
4. Copy and paste the URL for the example dataset on the dialog window
5. Click *Clone*

A notification on the bottom-right corner will let you know when the *cloning* is complete, and you should see a list of files on JupyterLab. All the files, except for `manifest.yaml` are files that belong to the dataset in the research repository. The file `manifest.yaml` is automatically created by the Fairly Toolset, and it contains metadata from the research data repository, such as:

- Authors
- Keywords
- License
- DOI
- Files in the dataset
- etc.

3.3 Part 2: Create a Fairly Dataset

Here, we show you how can you create and prepare your own dataset using the JupyterLab extension of *fairly*.

1. Create a new directory called `mydataset` inside the *workshop* directory.
2. Inside `workshop/mydataset/.` Open the context menu and click on *Create Fairly Dataset*
3. Select *Zenodo* as template from the drop-down list. *Notice that there are templates for other data repositories.*
4. Click *Create*. A `manifest.yaml` file will be add to the *dummy-data* directory. This file contains a list of fields that you can edit to add metadata to your dataset.

3.3.1 Include Files in your Dataset

Add some files to the `mydataset` directory. You can add files of your own, but be careful not to include anything that you want to keep confidential. Also consider the size of the files you will add, the larger the size the longer the upload will take. Also remember that for the current Zenodo API each file should be 100MB or smaller; this will change in the future.

If you do not want to use your own files, you can download and use the [dummy-data](#)

After you have added some file and/or folders to `mydataset`, JupyterLab should look something like this:

3.3.2 Editing the Manifest

The `manifest.yaml` file contains several sections to describe the metadata of a dataset. Some of the sections and fields are compulsory (they are required by the research data repository), others are optional. In this example you started a *fairly* dataset using the template for the Zenodo repository, but you could also do so for 4TU.ResearchData.

However, if you are not sure which repository you will use to publish a dataset, use the *Default* template. This template contains the most common sections and fields for the repositories supported by the Fairly Toolset.

Tip: Independently of which template you use to start a dataset, the `manifest.yaml` file is interoperable between data repositories, with very few exceptions. This means that you can use the same manifest file for various data repositories. Different templates are provided only as a guide to indicate what metadata is more relevant for each data repository.

1. Open the `manifest.yaml` file using the context menu, or by double-clicking on the file

2. Substitute the content of the `manifest.yaml` with the text below. *Here, we use only a small set of fields that are possible for Zenodo.*

```

metadata:
  type: dataset
  publication_date: '2023-08-31'
  title: My Title
  authors:
    - fullname: Surname, FirstName
      affiliation: Your institution
  description: A dataset from the Fairly Toolset workshop
  access_type: open
  license: CC0-1.0
  doi: ''
  prerelease_doi:
  keywords:
    - fairly-toolset
    - tutorial
    - dummy data

```

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```
notes: ''
related_identifiers: []
communities: []
grants: []
subjects: []
version: 1.0.0
language: eng
template: zenodo
files:
  includes:
  - ARP1_.info
  - ARP1_d01.zip
  - my_code.py
  - Survey_AI.csv
  - wind-mill.jpg
  excludes: []
```

3. Edit the dataset metadata by typing the information you want to add. For example, you can change the title, authors, description, etc. Save the file when you are done.

Important:

- The `includes` field must list the files and directories (folders) you want to include as part of the dataset. *Included files and directories will be uploaded to the the data repository*
 - The `excludes` field can be used for explicitly indicating what files or directories you **don't want to be part of the dataset**, for example, files that contain sensitive information. Excluded files and directories will never be uploaded to the data repository.
 - Files and directories that are not listed in either `includes` or `excludes` will be ignored by *fairly*.
-

3.4 Part 3: Upload Dataset to Repository

This part explains how to upload a dataset to an existing account in Zenodo. If you do not have an account yet, you can [sign up in this webpage](#).

3.4.1 Create Personal Token

A personal token is a way in which data repositories identify a user. We need to register a personal token for creating datasets in the repository and uploading files to an specific account.

1. Sign in to Zenodo.
2. On the top-right corner click on drop-down arrow, then *Applicaitons*.
3. On the section *Personal access tokens*, click the *New token* button.
4. Enter a name for your token, for example: `workshop`
5. For scopes, check all three boxes, and click *Create*
6. Copy the token (list of characters in red) to somewhere secure. **You will only see the token once.**
7. Under *Scopes*, check all three boxes once more. Then click *Save*

Personal access token / workshop

Access token

rww9br11AZnhmM...SNEGG...MmM...TPe0M6erxx

Please copy the personal access token now. You won't see it again!

Do not share this personal access token. It gives full access to your account.

Name

Name of personal access token.

Scopes

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> deposit:actions <small>Allow publishing of uploads.</small>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> deposit:write <small>Allow upload (but not publishing).</small>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> user:email <small>Allow access to email address (read-only).</small>
---	---	--

Scopes assign permissions to your personal access token. A personal access token works just like a normal OAuth access token for authentication against the API.

🗑 Delete
✓ Save

3.4.2 Register Personal Token

To register a personal token to the Fairly Toolset, do the following in JupyterLab:

1. Open the *Fairly* menu on the top menu bar, and click on *Add Repository Token*
2. Select *Zenodo* from the drop-down list.
3. Paste the token you copied from Zenodo in the previous step.
4. Click *Add Token*

Important:

- You can register tokens for other repositories supported by *fairly* in the same way. Tokens added in this way are global, and will be used by the JupyterLab extension, the Python package and the CLI.
- Tokens are stored in a file called `config.json` in your user home directory. This file is created automatically by

fairly when you register a token. For Windows the file is located in `C:\Users\<<You-user-name>\.fairly\config.json`, and for Linux/MacOS in `~/.fairly/config.json`.

- To **update a token**, simply register a new token with the same name. The old token will be replaced by the new one. To **remove a token**, simply repeat the process, but type a random character in the token field.
-

Warning: If you are using the Fairly Toolset in a shared computer, make sure that you **remove your tokens** from the JupyterLab extension. Otherwise, other users of the computer will be able to use your token to create datasets in your account.

Note: Windows users might need to re-start JupyterLab for the tokens to work correctly when uploading datasets.

3.4.3 Upload Dataset

1. On the left panel, do right-click, and then click *Upload Dataset*
2. Select Zenodo from the down-down list, and click *Continue*
3. Confirm that you want to upload the dataset to Zenodo by ticking the checkbox.
4. Click *OK*. A notification on the bottom-right corner will let you know that the upload is in progress and when it is complete.
5. Go to your Zenodo account and click on *Upload*. The *my dataset* dataset should be there.

Explore the dataset and notice that all the files and metadata you added in JupyterLab has been automatically added to the new dataset. You should also notice that the dataset is not **published**, this is on purpose. This gives you the opportunity to review the dataset before deciding to publish if, and if necessary to make changes. In this way we also prevent users to publish dataset by mistake.

Note: If you try to upload the dataset again, you will get an error message. This is because the dataset already exists in Zenodo. You can see this reflected in the `manifest.yaml` file; the section `remotes:` is added to the file after successfully uploading a dataset. It lists the names and ids of the repositories where the dataset has been uploaded. In the future, we will add a feature to allow users to update and sync datasets between repositories.

3.5 Part 4: Pushing Changes to Data Repository

In the last part of this tutorial, we will show you how to push changes to a dataset that has already been uploaded to a data repository. For this, we will use the dataset we created in the previous part.

Attention: To be able to push updates to an existing dataset in a repository, you need to have write access to the dataset. For most of the repositories this requires you to be the **owner** of the dataset. Most data repositories prevent updates if a dataset is “published” (i.e. editing is limited to datasets that are not yet published).

You can make changes to the files in a local dataset as you would normally do. For example, you can add new files, edit existing files, or delete files. You can also edit the `manifest.yaml` file to update the metadata of the dataset. If file inclusion or exclusion rules are defined using patterns (e.g. `*.txt`), then the extension automatically identifies added, removed, or modified files. Otherwise, you need to explicitly indicate what needs to be *included* or *excluded* by updating the `includes` and `excludes` fields in the `manifest.yaml` file.

The screenshot displays the Fairly Toolset interface. The top menu bar includes File, Edit, View, Run, Kernel, Fairly, Tabs, Settings, and Help. The left panel shows a file browser for the directory /mydataset/. The file list includes ARP1_.info, ARP1_d01.zip, manifest.yaml, my_code.py, new_file.py (highlighted), Survey_AI.csv, and wind-mill.jpg. The right panel shows the manifest.yaml file content:

```
15 keywords:
16 - workshop
17 - dummy data
18 notes: ''
19 related_identifiers: []
20 communities: []
21 grants: []
22 subjects: []
23 version: 1.0.0
24 language: eng
25 template: zenodo
26 files:
27 includes:
28 - ARP1_.info
29 - ARP1_d01.zip
30 - my_code.py
31 - Survey_AI.csv
32 - '*.jpg'
33 - new_file.py
34 excludes:
35 remotes:
36 zenodo:
37 id: '8350290'
38
```

Once you have made and **shaved** the changes, you can do the following upload the changes to the data repository.

1. On the left panel, do right-click,
2. click *Push* option from the list,
3. confirm that you want to push the changes and click *Push* button. A notification on the bottom-right corner will let you know that changes are in progress and when they are completed.

The image shows a file explorer window for a directory named `/ mydataset /`. The file list includes:

Name	Last Modified
ARP1_info	6 months ago
ARP1_d01.zip	6 months ago
Y: manifest.yaml	a minute ago
my_code.py	6 months ago
new_file.py	3 minutes ago
Survey_AI.csv	6 months ago
wind-mill.jpg	6 months ago

A red number **1** is positioned to the left of the `new_file.py` entry. A context menu is open over `new_file.py`, with the `Push` option highlighted and a red number **2** next to it. The menu items are:

- Paste (Ctrl+V)
- New File
- New Notebook
- New Folder
- Create Fairly Dataset
- Edit Dataset Metadata
- Clone Dataset
- Upload Dataset
- Push**

At the bottom of the menu, it says "Shift+Right Click for Browser Menu".

The code editor shows the following JSON content:

```
18 notes: ''
19 related_identifiers: []
20 communities: []
21 grants: []
22 subjects: []
23 version: 1.0.0
24 language: eng
25 template: zenodo
26 files:
27   includes:
28     - ARP1_info
29     - ARP1_d01.zip
30     - my_code.py
31     - Survey_AI.csv
32     - '*.jpg'
33     - new_file.py
34   excludes:
35 remotes:
zenodo:
  id: '8350290'
```


Tip: To push change to a dataset that you own, but you did not create using the Fairly Toolset, all you have to do is to clone it first, using the *Clone Dataset* option from the context menu. Then you will be able to make changes to the dataset and push them back to the data repository.

USING THE CLI

This tutorial shows how to use the *fairly* Command Line Interface (CLI) to clone, and create datasets, and to edit their metadata.

Important: Windows Users. For the following to work, you need Python in the PATH environment variable on Windows. If you're not sure that is the case, open the Shell, and type `python --version`. You should see the version of Python on the screen. If you see otherwise, follow these steps to [add Python to the PATH on Windows](#)

1. Open a *Terminal* or *Shell*
2. Test the *fairly* CLI is accessible in your terminal, by calling the help command:

```
fairly --help
```

You should see the following:

```
Usage: fairly [OPTIONS] COMMAND [ARGS]...

- Options_
├── --install-completion [bash|zsh|fish|powershell|pwsh] Install_
│   completion for the specified shell. [default: None]
├── --show-completion [bash|zsh|fish|powershell|pwsh] Show completion_
│   for the specified shell, to copy it or customize | the_
│   installation. | [default: None]_
├── --help Show this_
│   message and exit. |
- Commands_
├── config _
├── dataset _
├── list-repos List all repositories supported by fairly _
├── list-user-datasets List all datasets in the specified repository by_
```

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```
↪doi, title, and publication_date
```

4.1 Cloning a Dataset

1. Create a new directory and subdirectory `workshop/clone`

```
# On Windows
mkdir workshop
mkdir workshop\clone

# On Linux/MacOS
mkdir -p workshop/clone
```

2. Go to the `clone` directory

```
# On Windows
cd workshop\clone

# On Linux/MacOS
cd workshop/clone
```

3. Clone this [Zenodo dataset](https://zenodo.org/record/7748718#.ZBo1SNLMJhF), using its URL:

```
fairly dataset clone --url https://zenodo.org/record/7748718#.ZBo1SNLMJhF
```

4. Explore the content of the dataset, notice that file(s) of the dataset have been downloaded and its metadata is in the `manifest.yaml` file.

```
manifest.yaml Trixi.jl-v0.5.14.zip
```

4.2 Creating a Local fairly Dataset

We can use the CLI to initialize a new dataset.

1. Create a new directory called `mydataset-cli` inside the `workshop` directory. Then move to into the directory

```
# On Windows/Linux/McOS
mkdir mydataset-cli
cd mydataset-cli
```

2. Create a local dataset using the Zenodo metadata template, as follows

```
fairly dataset create zenodo
```

4.2.1 Include Files in your Dataset

Add some folders and files to the `mydataset-cli` directory. You can do this using the file explorer/browser. You can add files of your own, but be careful not to include anything that you want to keep confidential. Also consider the total size of the files you will add, the larger the size the longer the upload will take. Also remember that for the current Zenodo API each file should be 100MB or smaller; this will change in the future.

If you do not want to use files from your own, you can download and use the `dummy-data`

4.2.2 Editing the Manifest

The `manifest.yaml` file contains several sections to describe the metadata of a dataset. Some of the sections and fields are compulsory (they are required by the data repository), others are optional. In this example, you started a *fairly* dataset using the template for the Zenodo repository, but you could also do so for 4TU.ResearchData.

However, if you are not sure which repository you will use to publish a dataset, use the *default* option. This template contains the most common sections and fields for the repositories supported by *fairly*

Tip: Independently of which template you use to start a dataset, the `manifest.yaml` file is interoperable between data repositories, with very few exceptions. This means that you can use the same manifest file for various data repositories. Different templates are provided only as a guide to indicate what metadata is more relevant for each data repository.

1. Open the `manifest.yaml` using a text editor. On Linux/MacOS you can use **nano** or **vim**. On Windows use the **notepad**
2. Substitute the content of the `manifest.yaml` with the text below. *Here, we use only a small set of fields that are possible for Zenodo.*

```

metadata:
  type: dataset
  publication_date: '2023-03-22'
  title: My Title CLI
  authors:
    - fullname: Surname, FirstName
      affiliation: Your institution
  description: A dataset from the Fairly Toolset workshop
  access_type: open
  license: CC0-1.0
  doi: ''
  prereserve_doi:
  keywords:
    - workshop
    - dummy data
  notes: ''
  related_identifiers: []
  communities: []
  grants: []
  subjects: []
  version: 1.0.0
  language: eng
template: zenodo
files:
  includes:

```

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```
- ARP1_.info
- ARP1_d01.zip
- my_code.py
- Survey_AI.csv
- wind-mill.jpg
```

```
excludes: []
```

3. Edit the dataset metadata by typing the information you want to add. For example, you can change the title, authors, description, etc. Save the file when you are done.

Important:

- The `includes` field must list the files and directories (folders) you want to include as part of the dataset. *Included files and directories will be uploaded to the the data repository*
- The `excludes` field can be used for explicitly indicating what files or directories you **don't want to be part of the dataset**, for example, files that contain sensitive information. Excluded files and directories will never be uploaded to the data repository.
- Files and directories that are not listed in either `includes` or `excludes` will be ignored by *fairly*.

4.3 Upload Dataset to Data Repository

Here, we explain how to upload a dataset to an existing account in Zenodo. If you do not have an account yet, you can [sign up in this webpage](#).

For this, you first need to *Create Personal Token* and register it manually or *via JupyterLab*.

4.3.1 Upload Dataset

1. On the terminal or command prompt, type:

```
fairly dataset upload zenodo
```

2. Go to your Zenodo and click on *Upload*. The *My dataset CLI* dataset should be there.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the Zenodo logo on the left, a search bar in the center, and 'Upload' and 'Communities' buttons on the right. Below the header, there is a search bar for uploads. The main content area shows a navigation bar with 'Drafts 3', 'Published 3', and 'All versions'. Below this, a dataset card is visible for 'My Dataset CLI', created on March 22, 2023, at 12:18:43 AM and modified at 12:18:53 AM. The card includes a version tag 'March 22, 2023 (1.0.0)', a 'Dataset' label, and an 'Open Access' button.

Explore the dataset and notice that all the files and metadata you added in JupyterLab has been automatically added to the new dataset. You should also notice that the dataset is not **published**, this is on purpose. This gives you the opportunity to review the dataset before deciding to publish if, and if necessary to make changes. In this way we also prevent users to publish dataset by mistake.

Note: If you try to upload the dataset again, you will get an error message. This is because the dataset already exists in Zenodo. You can see this reflected in the `manifest.yaml` file; the section `remotes:` is added to the file after successfully uploading a dataset. It lists the names and ids of the repositories where the dataset has been uploaded. In the future, we will add a feature to allow users to update and sync datasets between repositories.

USING THE PYTHON API

In this tutorial you will learn how to use *fairly* as a Python package to clone, create and upload datasets to research data repositories.

If you haven't done so, *install the fairly package*.

5.1 Cloning a dataset

The Python API provides the flexibility to explore the metadata of a remote dataset before downloading it. A remote dataset is any dataset which is not stored locally.

1. In a python script, import the `fairly` package and open a remote dataset:

```
[1]: import fairly

# Open a remote dataset
dataset = fairly.dataset("doi:10.4121/21588096.v1")
```

2. You can now explore the metadata of the dataset as follows:

```
[2]: dataset.id
```

```
[2]: {'id': '21588096', 'version': '1'}
```

```
[3]: dataset.url
```

```
[3]: 'https://data.4tu.nl/datasets/a37120e2-96db-48e4-bd65-a54b970bc4fe/1'
```

```
[5]: print(dataset.size)
```

```
# number of files
len(dataset.files)
```

```
33339
```

```
[5]: 6
```

```
[6]: # complete metadata
dataset.metadata
```

```
[6]: Metadata({'authors': [Person({'fullname': 'Stefan Nielsen', 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-9214-
↳ 2932', 'figshare_id': 12882551})], 'keywords': ['Earthquakes', 'artificial neural
↳ network', 'precursor'], 'description': '<p>These are the accuracy results for the
↳ whole dataset A and B together. This is a second batch (2/2) of cycles where network
↳ was trained, tested and verified 50 times with different combinations of test, train
↳ and verification groups. There is a first batch of 50 in a separate file</p>', 'license
↳ ': {'id': 2, 'name': 'CC0', 'url': 'https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/
↳ '}, 'title': 'Earthquake Precursors detected by convolutional neural network', 'doi':
↳ '10.4121/21588096.v1', 'type': 'dataset', 'access_type': 'open', 'custom_fields': {
↳ 'Time coverage': '2012-2022', 'Publisher': '4TU.ResearchData', 'Organizations':
↳ 'University of Durham, Department of Earth Sciences.', 'Geolocation Longitude': '138.
↳ 204', 'Geolocation Latitude': '36.546', 'Geolocation': 'Japan and surrounding area',
↳ 'Format': '*.py, *.csv, *.txt'}, 'categories': [13555], 'online_date': '2022-11-24T07:
↳ 50:39'})
```

3. You can save the dataset's metadata to a file to a local directory as follows. The directory will be created if it does not exist.

```
[7]: # store dataset locally (i.e. clone dataset)
local_dataset = dataset.store("./cloned-dataset")
```

5.2 Creating a local dataset

A `local dataset` is a dataset which is stored locally. When creating our own dataset, we used a local dataset.

1. Initialize a new dataset:

```
[2]: import fairly

# Initialize a local dataset
dataset = fairly.init_dataset("./local-dataset") # path is created if it does not exist
```

2. Set the dataset's metadata attributes by passing a list of attribute names and values to a local dataset:

```
[9]: dataset.set_metadata(
    title="My first dataset",
    keywords=[ "fairly", "python", "api" ],
    authors=[ "0000-0002-0516-185X",
              { "name": "Jane", "surname": "Doe" }
            ],
)
```

```
[10]: # Metadata attributes can be passed one by one as follows
dataset.metadata["license"] = "CC-BY-4.0"
```

3. Add files and folders to the dataset:

```
[11]: dataset.includes.extend([
    "README",
    "*.csv",
    "train/*.jpg"
])
```

4. To save values to the dataset's attributes to the `manifest.yaml` file, we must call the `save()` method:

```
[12]: # Save changes and update manifest.yaml
dataset.save()
```

5.3 Uploading a dataset

To upload a dataset to a research data repository, we must first register an access token for an account in the data repository. Check the tutorial on the *JupyterLab extension* to learn how to register an access token.

Once you have registered an access token, you can upload a dataset with a single command:

```
[ ]: # Upload dataset to data repository
remotte_dataset = dataset.upload('zenodo')
```

5.4 Pushing changes to a data repository

After uploading a dataset to a data repository, you can use the `push` command to push changes to the dataset's metadata and files and update the data repository. The `push` method automatically finds the remote version of a dataset from the information available in the *manifest* file. It also updates the remote metadata, if any metadata fields are modified locally.

To be able to push updates to an existing dataset in a repository, you need to have write access to the dataset. For most of the repositories this requires you to be the owner of the dataset. Most data repositories prevent updates if a dataset is “published” (i.e. editing is limited to datasets that are not yet published).

5.4.1 Changing metadata in a dataset

For example, to update the *title* of a dataset for which you have a local copy, you can do the following:

```
[4]: ds = fairly.dataset("./local-dataset")
ds.metadata["title"] = "New title"
ds.save_metadata() # save changes to manifest.yaml

ds.push() # push changes to data repository to update an existing dataset
```

5.4.2 Changing files in a dataset

You can add, remove, or modify files in a local dataset as you wish. If file inclusion or exclusion rules are defined using patterns (e.g. `'*.txt'`), then fairly automatically identifies added, removed, or modified files. Otherwise, you need to explicitly indicate what needs to be *included* or *excluded*. Use the `includes.append` and `excludes.append` methods to do so.

```
[6]: # include a new file or directory
ds.includes.append("new file.txt")

# remove a file or directory
ds.excludes.append("old file.txt")
```

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```
ds.save() # save changes to manifest.yaml
```

Once the changes are saved to the *manifest file*, the remote version can be updated by calling the `push` method:

```
[ ]: ds.push() # push changes to data repository
```

To learn more about the Fairly Python API, check the [API reference](#).

6.1 fairly package

6.1.1 Subpackages

fairly.client package

Submodules

fairly.client.djehuty module

class `fairly.client.djehuty.DjehutyClient`(*repository_id: str = None, **kwargs*)

Bases: *FigshareClient*

4TU.ResearchData is using *custom_fields* to store the following information:

- Contributors
- Data Link
- Derived From
- Format
- Geolocation Latitude
- Geolocation Longitude
- Geolocation
- Language
- Licence remarks
- Organizations
- Publisher
- Same As
- Time coverage

From the developers:

> The use of “Data Link” is inconsistent, so try to avoid using it. In > djehuty, we will assign “Data Link” values as “file links” where > applicable (so they show up under “files”). I think also “Organizations” > and “Publisher” are not entirely consistent and will have gone through > manual cleanup once djehuty goes live.

```
REGEXP_UUID = re.compile('^[a-f\d+)(-[a-f\d+)+$', re.IGNORECASE)
```

fairly.client.figshare module

```
class fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient(repository_id: str = None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *Client*

```
LOCKED_SLEEP = 5
```

```
LOCKED_TRIES = 5
```

```
PAGE_SIZE = 25
```

```
property categories: Dict
```

```
get_categories(refresh: bool = False) → Dict
```

```
classmethod get_config(**kwargs) → Dict
```

```
classmethod get_config_parameters() → Dict
```

Returns configuration parameters

Parameters

None –

Returns

Dictionary of configuration parameters. Keys are the parameter names, values are the descriptions.

```
get_details(id: Dict) → Dict
```

Returns standard details of the specified dataset.

Details dictionary:

- title (str): Title
- url (str): URL address
- doi (str): DOI
- status (str): Status
- size (int): Total size of data files in bytes
- created (datetime.datetime): Creation date and time
- modified (datetime.datetime): Last modification date and time

Possible statuses are as follows:

- “draft”: Dataset is not published yet.
- “public”: Dataset is published and is publicly available.
- “embargoed”: Dataset is published, but is under embargo.
- “restricted”: Dataset is published, but accessible only under certain conditions.
- “closed”: Dataset is published, but accessible only by the owners.
- “unknown”: Dataset is in an unknown state.

Parameters**id** (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id**Returns**

Details dictionary of the dataset.

get_files(*id: Dict*) → List[*RemoteFile*]**record_type_lookup** = {'conference contribution': 'conferencepaper', 'journal contribution': 'article', 'media': 'video', 'online resource': 'onlineresource'}**record_types** = {'book': 'Book', 'conference contribution': 'Conference Contribution', 'dataset': 'Dataset', 'figure': 'Figure', 'journal contribution': 'Journal Contribution', 'media': 'Media', 'online resource': 'Online Resource', 'poster': 'Poster', 'preprint': 'Preprint', 'presentation': 'Presentation', 'software': 'Software', 'thesis': 'Thesis'}**save_metadata**(*id: Dict, metadata: Metadata*) → None

Saves metadata of the specified dataset

Parameters

- **id** (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id
- **metadata** (*Metadata*) – Metadata to be saved

Returns

None

Raises**ValueError**("No access token") –**classmethod supports_folder**() → bool

Returns if folders are supported.

validate_metadata(*metadata: Metadata*) → Dict

Validates metadata

Parameters**metadata** (*Metadata*) – Metadata to be validated**Returns**

Dictionary of invalid metadata fields and related error messages, if any.

fairly.client.zenodo module**class** **fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient**(*repository_id: str = None, **kwargs*)Bases: *Client***_details**

Record details cache

Type

Dict

KEEP_ALIVE = 10**PAGE_SIZE** = 100

```
access_rights = {'closed': 'Closed Access', 'embargoed': 'Embargoed Access', 'open': 'Open Access', 'restricted': 'Restricted Access'}
```

`get_communities()` → List[Dict]

Retrieves the list of available communities

WARNING: This is a slow function due to downloads

Community dictionary:

- id (str): Unique id
- name (str): Name of the community
- url (str): URL address of the community page at Zenodo
- logo_url (str): URL address of the community logo
- created (str): Creation date of the community
- last_record_accepted (str): Date of the last record accepted
- description (str): Short description of the community
- about (str): Long description of the community
- curation_policy (str): Curation policy of the community

Returns

List of community dictionaries

Raises

None –

classmethod `get_config(**kwargs)` → Dict

classmethod `get_config_parameters()` → Dict

Returns configuration parameters

Parameters

None –

Returns

Dictionary of configuration parameters. Keys are the parameter names, values are the descriptions.

`get_details(id: Dict)` → Dict

Returns standard details of the specified dataset.

Details dictionary:

- title (str): Title
- url (str): URL address
- doi (str): DOI
- status (str): Status
- size (int): Total size of data files in bytes
- created (datetime.datetime): Creation date and time
- modified (datetime.datetime): Last modification date and time

Possible statuses are as follows:

- “draft”: Dataset is not published yet.
- “public”: Dataset is published and is publicly available.
- “embargoed”: Dataset is published, but is under embargo.
- “restricted”: Dataset is published, but accessible only under certain conditions.
- “closed”: Dataset is published, but accessible only by the owners.
- “error”: Dataset is in an error state.
- “unknown”: Dataset is in an unknown state.

Parameters

id (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id

Returns

Details dictionary of the dataset.

get_files(*id: Dict*) → List[*RemoteFile*]

get_funders() → List[*Dict*]

Retrieves the list of available funders

WARNING: This is a slow function due to downloads

Funder dictionary:

- id (str): Unique id (= DOI)
- name (str): Name of the funder
- type (str): Type of the funder
- subtype (str): Subtype of the funder
- country (str): Country code of the funder
- acronyms (list): Acronyms of the funder

For the complete list of data fields check the JSON schema available at: <http://zenodo.org/schemas/funders/funder-v1.0.0.json>

Returns

List of funder dictionaries

Raises

None –

```
grant_dois: {'10.13039/501100000923': 'Australian Research Council',
'10.13039/501100002428': 'Austrian Science Fund', '10.13039/501100000780': 'European
Commission', '10.13039/501100000806': 'European Environment Agency',
'10.13039/501100002341': 'Academy of Finland', '10.13039/501100004488': 'Hrvatska
Zaklada za Znanost', '10.13039/501100001871': 'Fundação para a Ciência e a
Tecnologia', '10.13039/501100004564': 'Ministarstvo Prosvete, Nauke i Tehnološkog
Razvoja', '10.13039/501100006588': 'Ministarstvo Znanosti, Obrazovanja i Sporta',
'10.13039/501100000925': 'National Health and Medical Research Council',
'10.13039/100000002': 'National Institutes of Health', '10.13039/100000001':
'National Science Foundation', '10.13039/501100003246': 'Nederlandse Organisatie
voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek', '10.13039/501100000690': 'Research Councils',
'10.13039/501100001711': 'Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der
wissenschaftlichen Forschung', '10.13039/501100001602': 'Science Foundation
Ireland', '10.13039/100004440': 'Wellcome Trust'}
```

```
image_types = {'diagram': 'Diagram', 'drawing': 'Drawing', 'figure': 'Figure',
              'photo': 'Photo', 'plot': 'Plot'}
```

```
publication_types = {'annotationcollection': 'Annotation collection', 'article':
                    'Journal article', 'book': 'Book', 'conferencepaper': 'Conference paper',
                    'datamanagementplan': 'Data management plan', 'deliverable': 'Project deliverable',
                    'milestone': 'Project milestone', 'patent': 'Patent', 'preprint': 'Preprint',
                    'proposal': 'Proposal', 'report': 'Report', 'section': 'Book section',
                    'softwaredocumentation': 'Software documentation', 'taxonomictreatment': 'Taxonomic
                    treatment', 'technicalnote': 'Technical note', 'thesis': 'Thesis', 'workingpaper':
                    'Working paper'}
```

```
record_types = {'dataset': 'Dataset', 'image': 'Image', 'lesson': 'Lesson', 'other':
                'Other', 'physicalobject': 'Physical object', 'poster': 'Poster', 'presentation':
                'Presentation', 'publication': 'Publication', 'software': 'Software', 'video':
                'Video/Audio'}
```

```
relations: {'isCitedBy': 'is cited by', 'cites': 'cites', 'isSupplementTo': 'is
supplement to', 'isSupplementedBy': 'is supplemented by', 'isContinuedBy': 'is
continued by', 'continues': 'continues', 'isDescribedBy': 'is described by',
'describes': 'describes', 'hasMetadata': 'has metadata', 'isMetadataFor': 'is
metadata for', 'isNewVersionOf': 'is new version of', 'isPreviousVersionOf': 'is
previous version of', 'isPartOf': 'is part of', 'hasPart': 'has part',
'isReferencedBy': 'is referenced by', 'references': 'references', 'isDocumentedBy':
'is documented by', 'documents': 'documents', 'isCompiledBy': 'is compiled by',
'compiles': 'compiles', 'isVariantFormOf': 'is variant form of', 'isOriginalFormof':
'is original form of', 'isIdenticalTo': 'is identical to', 'isAlternateIdentifier':
'is alternative identifier', 'isReviewedBy': 'is reviewed by', 'reviews': 'reviews',
'isDerivedFrom': 'is derived from', 'isSourceOf': 'is source of', 'requires':
'requires', 'isRequiredBy': 'is required by', 'isObsoletedBy': 'is obsoleted by',
'obsoletes': 'obsoletes'}
```

`save_metadata(id: Dict, metadata: Metadata) → None`

Saves metadata of the specified dataset

Parameters

- `id` (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id
- `metadata` (*Metadata*) – Metadata to be saved

Returns

None

Raises

`ValueError("No access token")` –

`classmethod supports_folder()` → bool

Returns if folders are supported.

`validate_metadata(metadata: Metadata) → Dict`

Validates metadata

Parameters

- `metadata` (*Metadata*) – Metadata to be validated

Returns

Dictionary of invalid metadata fields and related error messages, if any.

Module contents

class `fairly.client.Client`(*repository_id: str = None, **kwargs*)

Bases: ABC

config

Configuration options

Type

dict

_session

HTTP session object

Type

Session

_datasets

Public dataset cache

Type

dict

_account_datasets

Account dataset cache

Type

List

_licenses

Licenses cache

Type

List

Class Attributes:

REGEXP_URL: Regular expression to validate URL address. REQUEST_FORMAT: Request data format

CHUCK_SIZE: Data transfer chunk size

CHUNK_SIZE = 65536

REGEXP_URL = `re.compile('^[http(s)?://\\/(www\\.)?a-zA-Z0-9@:%._\\+~#=#]{2,256}\\.[a-z]{2,6}\\b([-a-zA-Z0-9@:%_\\+\\.~#?&/=]*)$')`, `re.IGNORECASE`)

REQUEST_FORMAT = 'json'

property `client_id: str`

Client identifier

create_dataset(*metadata=None*) → *RemoteDataset*

Creates a dataset with the specified metadata

Parameters

metadata – Metadata of the dataset (optional)

Returns

Dataset

Raises

- **ValueError("Invalid metadata")** –
- **ValueError("Invalid metadata", validation_result)** –

delete_dataset(*id*, ***kwargs*) → None

Deletes specified dataset from the repository

Parameters

- **id** – Dataset identifier
- ****kwargs** – Other identifier arguments

Returns

None

delete_file(*dataset*, *file*) → None

download_file(*file*: [RemoteFile](#), *path*: *str* = None, *name*: *str* = None, *notify*: *Callable* = None) → [LocalFile](#)

Downloads a remote file.

Parameters

- **file** ([RemoteFile](#)) – Remote file.
- **path** (*str*) – Local path of the file (optional).
- **name** (*str*) – Local name of the file (optional).
- **notify** (*Callable*) – Notification callback method (optional).

Returns

Local file object.

Raises

- **ValueError("No URL address")** – If remote file has no URL address.
- **IOError("Invalid MD5 checksum")** – If MD5 checksum is invalid.

get_account_datasets(*refresh*: *bool* = False) → List[[RemoteDataset](#)]

classmethod get_config(***kwargs*) → Dict

classmethod get_config_parameters() → Dict

Returns configuration parameters

Parameters

None –

Returns

Dictionary of configuration parameters. Keys are the parameter names, values are the descriptions.

get_dataset(*id*=None, *refresh*: *bool* = False, ***kwargs*) → [RemoteDataset](#)

get_dataset_id(*id*=None, ***kwargs*) → Dict

Returns standard dataset identifier

Parameters

- **id** – Dataset identifier
- ****kwargs** – Other identifier arguments

Returns

Standard dataset identifier

abstract get_details(*id: Dict*) → Dict

Returns standard details of the specified dataset.

Details dictionary:

- title (str): Title
- url (str): URL address
- doi (str): DOI
- status (str): Status
- size (int): Total size of data files in bytes
- created (datetime.datetime): Creation date and time
- modified (datetime.datetime): Last modification date and time

Possible statuses are as follows:

- “draft”: Dataset is not published yet.
- “public”: Dataset is published and is publicly available.
- “embargoed”: Dataset is published, but is under embargo.
- “restricted”: Dataset is published, but accessible only under certain conditions.
- “closed”: Dataset is published, but accessible only by the owners.
- “error”: Dataset is in an error state.
- “unknown”: Dataset is in an unknown state.

Parameters

id (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id

Returns

Details dictionary of the dataset.

abstract get_files(*id: Dict*) → List[*RemoteFile*]

get_licenses(*refresh: bool = False*) → List[Dict]

Returns list of available licenses

Parameters

refresh (*bool*) – Set True to refresh licenses (default = False)

Returns

List of client-specific license dictionaries

get_metadata(*id: Dict*) → *Metadata*

Returns standard metadata of the specified dataset

Parameters

id (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id

Returns

Standard metadata

get_versions(*id*, *refresh*: *bool* = *False*, ***kwargs*) → List[*RemoteDataset*]

Returns datasets of all available versions of the specified dataset

Parameters

- **id** – Dataset identifier
- **refresh** (*bool*) – Set True to refresh versions (default = False)

Returns

List of datasets of all available versions

property licenses: Dict

classmethod normalize(*name*: *str*, *val*) → Any

Normalized metadata attribute value

Parameters

- **name** (*str*) – Attribute name
- **val** – Attribute value

Returns

Normalized attribute value

classmethod parse_id(*id*: *str*)

Parses the specified identifier

Returns

Tuple of identifier type and value

property repository_id: str

Repository identifier of the client

save_config(*save_environment*=*False*) → None

Saves client configuration.

Parameters

save_environment – Set True to save environment variables

Returns

None

abstract save_metadata(*id*: Dict, *metadata*: Metadata) → None

Saves metadata of the specified dataset

Parameters

- **id** (*Dict*) – Standard dataset id
- **metadata** (*Metadata*) – Metadata to be saved

Returns

None

abstract classmethod supports_folder() → bool

Returns if folders are supported.

upload_file(*dataset*, *file*, *notify*: Callable = None) → RemoteFile

abstract validate_metadata(*metadata*: [Metadata](#)) → Dict

Validates metadata

Parameters

metadata ([Metadata](#)) – Metadata to be validated

Returns

Dictionary of invalid metadata fields and related error messages, if any.

fairly.dataset package

Submodules

fairly.dataset.local module

class `fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset`(*path*: str, *auto_refresh*: bool = True)

Bases: [Dataset](#)

_path

Path of the dataset

Type

str

_manifest_path

Path of the dataset manifest

Type

str

_includes

File inclusion rules

Type

set

_excludes

File exclusion rules

Type

set

_md5s

MD5 hash cache of the files

Type

dict

_yaml

YAML object

Class Attributes:

`_regexps` (dict): Regular expression cache of the file rules

property created: datetime

Creation date and time of the dataset

property excludes: Set

Exclusion rules of the dataset files

get_archive_method() → str

Returns archiving method to be used for the dataset.

get_archive_name() → str

Returns archive name to be used for the dataset.

get_remote_dataset(remote=None) → *RemoteDataset*

property includes: Set

Inclusion rules of the dataset files

property modified: datetime

Last modification date and time of the dataset

property path: str

Path of the dataset

pull(source=None, notify: Callable = None) → None

push(target=None, notify: Callable = None) → *RemoteDataset*

property remote_datasets: Dict

Known remote datasets of the dataset.

reproduce() → *LocalDataset*

Reproduces an actual copy of the dataset.

save() → None

Saves metadata and file inclusion/exclusion rules.

save_files(force: bool = False) → None

Stores dataset file list if exists.

Parameters

force (*bool*) – Set True to enforce save even if existing dataset is modified

Returns

None

Raises

Warning("Existing dataset is modified") –

set_remote_dataset(dataset) → None

property size: int

Total size of the dataset in bytes.

synchronize(source, notify: Callable = None) → None

property template: str

Metadata template of the dataset

upload(repository=None, notify: Callable = None, strategy: str = 'auto', force: bool = False) → *RemoteDataset*

Uploads dataset to the repository.

Available upload strategies:

- `auto`: Mirror if folders are supported, otherwise archive folders individually.
- `mirror`: Upload files and folders as they are.
- `archive_all`: Create a single archive file for all files and folders.
- `archive_folders`: Create an individual archive file for each folder.

Parameters

- **repository** – Repository identifier or client. If not specified, template identifier is used.
- **notify** (*Callable*) – Notification callback function.
- **strategy** (*str*) – Folder upload strategy (default = “auto”)
- **force** (*bool*) – Set True to upload dataset even if a remote version exists (default = False)

Returns

Remote dataset

Raises

- **ValueError("Invalid repository")** – If repository argument is invalid.
- **ValueError("Invalid upload strategy")** – If upload strategy is invalid.
- **ValueError("Invalid archiving method")** – If archiving method is invalid.
- **ValueError("Invalid archive name")** – If archive name is invalid.
- **Warning("Remote dataset exists")** – If remote dataset exists.

fairly.dataset.remote module

```
class fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset(client, id=None, auto_refresh: bool = True, details: Dict = None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *Dataset*

_client

Client object

Type

Client

_id

Dataset identifier

Type

str

_details

Dataset details

Type

Dict

property client: *Client*

Client of the dataset

property created: *datetime*

Creation date and time of the dataset

property doi: str

DOI of the dataset.

get_versions() → List[*RemoteDataset*]

Returns all available versions of the dataset.

Returns

List of remote datasets of all available versions.

property id: Dict

Identifier of the dataset

property modified: datetime

Last modification date and time of the dataset

reproduce() → *RemoteDataset*

Reproduces an actual copy of the dataset.

property size: int

Total size of the dataset in bytes.

property status: str

Status of the dataset.

Possible statuses are as follows:

- “draft”: Dataset is not published yet.
- “public”: Dataset is published and is publicly available.
- “embargoed”: Dataset is published, but is under embargo.
- “restricted”: Dataset is published, but accessible only under certain conditions.
- “closed”: Dataset is published, but accessible only by the owners.
- “error”: Dataset is in an error state.
- “unknown”: Dataset is in an unknown state.

store(*path: str = None, notify: Callable = None, extract: bool = False*) → *LocalDataset*

Stores the dataset to a local directory.

If no path is provided, DOI is used by replacing slashes and backslashes with underscores. Local directory is created if it does not exist.

Parameters

- **path** (*str*) – Path to the local directory (optional).
- **notify** (*Callable*) – Notification callback method (optional).
- **extract** (*bool*) – Set True to extract archive files (default = False).

Returns

LocalDataset object of the stored local dataset.

Raises

- **ValueError**("Empty path") –
- **ValueError**("Directory is not empty") –

property title: str

Title of the dataset.

property url: str

URL address of the dataset.

Module contents

class `fairly.dataset.Dataset`(*auto_refresh: bool = False*)

Bases: ABC

`_metadata`

Metadata

Type

Metadata

`_files`

Files list

Type

list

`_modified`

Last known modification date

Type

datetime.datetime

`_auto_refresh`

Auto-refresh flag

Type

bool

property auto_refresh: bool

abstract property created: datetime

Creation date and time of the dataset.

diff_files(*dataset: Dataset = None*) → *Diff*

diff_metadata(*dataset: Dataset = None*)

file(*val: str*) → *File*

property files: List[File]

List of files of the dataset

get_file(*val: str, refresh: bool = False*) → *File*

get_files(*refresh: bool = False*) → Dict[str, *File*]

Returns dictionary of files of the dataset

Parameters

refresh (*bool*) – Set True to enforce file list retrieval

Returns

Dictionary of files of the dataset (key = path, value = File object)

get_metadata(*refresh: bool = False*) → *Metadata*

Returns metadata of the dataset

Parameters

refresh (*bool*) – Set True to enforce metadata retrieval

Returns

Metadata of the dataset

property is_modified: bool

Checks if the existing dataset is modified.

Returns

True if the existing dataset is modified, False otherwise.

property metadata: *Metadata*

Metadata of the dataset

abstract property modified: datetime

Last modification date and time of the dataset.

abstract reproduce() → *Dataset*

Reproduces an actual copy of the dataset.

save_metadata(*force: bool = False*) → None

Stores dataset metadata if exists

Parameters

force (*bool*) – Set True to enforce save even if existing dataset is modified

Returns

None

Raises

Warning("Existing dataset is modified") –

set_metadata(***kwargs*) → None

abstract property size: int

Total size of the dataset in bytes.

property title: str

Title of the dataset.

fairly.file package

Submodules

fairly.file.local module

LocalFile class module.

LocalFile class is used to perform operations on local files.

Usage example:

```

>>> file = LocalFile("/path/to/local/file/filename.txt")
>>> file.type
application/text
>>> file.size
543
>>> file.is_archive
False

```

```
class fairly.file.local.LocalFile(fullpath: str, basepath: str = None, md5: str = None)
```

Bases: *File*

LocalFile class.

Class Attributes:

CHUNK_SIZE: Chunk size in bytes to calculate MD5 checksum (default = 65536)

CHUNK_SIZE = 65536

extract(path: str = None, notify: Callable = None) → List

Extracts archive file contents to a specified directory.

Parameters

- **path** – Path of the directory to extract to. Default is the current working directory.
- **notify** – Notification callback function. Three arguments are provided to the callback function:
 - file (LocalFile): File object of the extracted local file
 - **current_size (int): Current total uncompressed size of extracted files.**
 - total_size (int): Total uncompressed size of the archive

Raises

- **ValueError("Invalid path")** – If path is not a directory path.
- **ValueError("Invalid archive item {name}")** – If archive item path is not valid.
- **ValueError("Invalid archive file")** – If file is not an archive file.

Returns

List of names of extracted files (str).

property fullpath: str

Full path of the file.

Returns

Full path of the file (str).

property is_archive: bool

Checks if file is an archive file.

Returns

True if file is an archive file, False otherwise.

match(val: str) → bool

Checks if file matches the specified file identifier.

Returns

True if file matches the specified file identifier, False otherwise.

property md5: str

MD5 checksum of the file.

Returns

MD5 checksum of the file (str).

property type: str

MIME type of the file.

Returns

MIME type of the file (str).

fairly.file.remote module

```
class fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile(url: str, id: str = None, path: str = None, size: int = None, type: str = None, md5: str = None)
```

Bases: *File*

property headers: str

property id: str

match(val: str) → bool

property md5: int

MD5 hash of the file.

property name: str

Name of the file including its extension.

property size: int

Size of the file in bytes.

property type: str

MIME type of the file.

property url: str

Module contents

```
class fairly.file.File
```

Bases: ABC

property extension: str

Extension of the file.

property is_simple: bool

Returns True if the file path does not include directories, i.e. the path is equal to the name.

match(val: str) → bool

property md5: str

MD5 hash of the file.

property name: str

Name of the file including its extension.

property path: str

Path of the file including its name.

property size: int

Size of the file in bytes.

property type: str

MIME type of the file.

6.1.2 Submodules

6.1.3 fairly.diff module

Diff class module.

Diff class is used to keep track of dataset modifications.

Usage example:

```
>>> diff = Diff()
>>> diff.modify("name", "Johnny", "John")
>>> diff.modified
{"name": ("Johnny", "John")}
```

class fairly.diff.Diff

Bases: object

_added

Items added

Type

Dict

_modified

Items modified

Type

Dict

_removed

Items removed

Type

Dict

add(key, val) → None

Appends an item to the diff set as added.

Parameters

- **key** – Item key
- **val** – Item value

property added: Dict

Returns a dictionary of added items.

property modified: Dict

Returns a dictionary of modified items.

modify(*key, val, oldval*) → None

Appends an item to the diff set as modified.

Parameters

- **key** – Item key
- **val** – Item value
- **oldVal** – Old value of the item

remove(*key, val*) → None

Appends an item to the diff set as removed.

Parameters

- **key** – Item key
- **val** – Item value

property removed: Dict

Returns a dictionary of removed items.

6.1.4 fairly.metadata module

Metadata class module.

Metadata class is used to store metadata attributes in a standardized manner.

Usage example:

```
>>> metadata = Metadata({"title": "Title", "DOI": "doi:xxx"})
>>> metadata["authors"] = ["Doe, John"]
```

class fairly.metadata.**Metadata**(*normalize: Callable = None, **kwargs*)

Bases: MutableMapping

Metadata class.

_normalize

Attribute normalization method.

Type

Callable

_attrs

Metadata attributes.

Type

Dict

_basis

Basis of metadata attributes.

Type

Dict

Class Attributes:

REGEXP_DOI: Regular expression to validate DOI.

`REGEXP_DOI = re.compile('^10.\d{4,9}/[-._;()/:a-z0-9]+$', re.IGNORECASE)`

`autocomplete(overwrite: bool = False, attrs: List = None, **kwargs) → Dict`

Completes missing metadata attributes by using the available information.

Parameters

- **overwrite** – Set True to overwrite existing attributes.
- **attrs** – List of attributes to be completed.
- ****kwargs** – Arguments for the specific autocomplete methods.

Returns

A dictionary of attributes set by method.

`property is_modified: bool`

Checks if metadata is modified.

Returns

True if metadata is modified, False otherwise.

`classmethod normalize(name: str, val) → Any`

Normalizes metadata attribute value.

Parameters

- **name** – Attribute name.
- **val** – Attribute value.

Returns

Normalized attribute value.

Raises

ValueError – If invalid attribute value.

`print()`

Pretty prints metadata.

`rebase()`

`serialize() → Dict`

Serializes metadata as a dictionary.

Returns

Metadata dictionary.

6.1.5 fairly.person module

Person class module.

Person class is used to store person (e.g. author) information in a standardized manner.

Usage example:

```
>>> person = Person("Doe, John")
>>> person = Person(fullname="Doe, Jon", orcid_id="xxx")
>>> person.affiliation = "fairly Community"
```

```
class fairly.person.Person(person: str = None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: MutableMapping

Class to handle person information, e.g. for authors, contributors, etc.

Class Attributes:

REGEXP_ORCID_ID: Regular expression to validate ORCID identifier. REGEXP_EMAIL: Regular expression to validate e-mail address.

```
REGEXP_EMAIL = re.compile('^[\\w\\.+-]+@[\\w-]+\\.([\\w-]{2,})$')
```

```
REGEXP_ORCID_ID = re.compile('^([\\d]{4}-){3}[\\d]{3}([\\d|X])$')
```

```
autocomplete(overwrite: bool = False, orcid_token: str = None) → Dict
```

Completes missing information by using the ORCID identifier.

Parameters

overwrite – If True existing attributes are overwritten.

Returns

A dictionary of attributes set by method.

```
static from_orcid_id(orcid_id: str, token: str = None) → Person
```

Retrieves person information from ORCID identifier.

If not specified, *token* is read from fairly configuration. If it is also not available, it is retrieved by using *get_orcid_token()* method.

Parameters

- **orcid_id** – ORCID identifier.
- **token** – ORCID access token.

Returns

Person object if valid ORCID identifier, otherwise None.

Raises

- **ValueError("No access token")** – If access token is not available.
- **ValueError("Invalid ORCID identifier")** – If ORCID identified is not valid.

```
static get_orcid_token(client_id: str = None, client_secret: str = None) → str
```

Retrieves ORCID access token by using ORCID client id and secret.

ORCID access token is required to retrieve person information by using an ORCID ID.

If not specified, *client_id* and *client_secret* are read from fairly configuration.

Parameters

- **client_id** – ORCID client id.
- **client_secret** – ORCID client secret.

Returns

ORCID access token.

Raises

- **ValueError("No client id")** – If client id is not available.
- **ValueError("No client secret")** – If client secret is not available.
- **ValueError("Invalid response")** – If access token is not retrieved.

static `get_persons(people)` → List[*Person*]

Returns standard person list from the people argument.

A string or an iterable are accepted as input. If input is a string, it is split using semicolon and line feed as separators. For the items of the iterable, the following are performed:

- If it is a Person object, a copy is created.
- If it is a string, it is parsed to a dictionary using `parse()`.
- If it is a dictionary, Person object is created.

Parameters

people – People argument.

Returns

List of person objects.

Raises

ValueError – If people argument is invalid.

classmethod `parse(person: str)` → Dict

Parses person identifier and extracts available person attributes.

The following attributes might be extracted:

- name
- surname
- fullname
- orcid_id

Parameters

person – Person identifier (e.g. fullname)

Returns

Dictionary of person attributes.

serialize() → Dict

Serializes person as a dictionary.

Returns

Person dictionary.

class `fairly.person.PersonList(iterable=None)`

Bases: list

append(item)

Append object to the end of the list.

extend(Iterable)

Extend list by appending elements from the iterable.

insert(index, item)

Insert object before index.

6.1.6 Module contents

fairly

`fairly.client(id: str, **kwargs) → Client`

Creates client object from a client or repository identifier.

Identifier is first checked within recognized repository identifiers. If no match is found, it is regarded as a client identifier. Additional client arguments (e.g. API URL address) might be necessary for the later.

Parameters

- **id** (*str*) – Client or repository identifier.
- ****kwargs** – Other client arguments.

Returns

Client object.

Raises

ValueError – If invalid client id.

Examples

```
>>> # Create a 4TU.ResearchData client (id = "4tu")
>>> client = fairly.client("4tu")
```

```
>>> # Create a Figshare client with a custom URL address
>>> client = fairly.client("figshare", url="https://data.4tu.nl/")
```

`fairly.dataset(id: str) → Dataset`

Creates dataset object from a dataset identifier.

The following types of dataset identifiers are supported:

- DOI : Digital object identifier of the remote dataset.
- URL : URL address of the remote dataset.
- Path : Path of the local dataset.

Repository of the dataset is automatically detected by checking the URL addresses and the DOI prefixes of the recognized repositories.

Parameters

id (*str*) – Dataset identifier.

Returns

Dataset object.

Raises

ValueError – If unknown dataset identifier.

Examples

```
>>> dataset = fairly.dataset("10.5281/zenodo.6026285")
>>> dataset = fairly.dataset("https://zenodo.org/record/6026285")
```

`fairly.get_clients()` → Dict

Returns available clients.

Returns

Dictionary of the available clients. Keys are client identifiers (str), values are client classes (Client).

Raises

AttributeError – If a client module is not valid.

Examples

```
>>> fairly.get_clients()
>>> {'figshare': <class 'fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient'>, ...}
```

`fairly.get_config(key: str)` → Dict

Returns configuration parameters for the specified key.

Configuration parameters are read from the following sources:

1. Configuration file of the package located at {package_root}/data/config.json
2. Configuration file of the user located at ~/.fairly/config.json.
3. Environmental variables of the user starting with FAIRLY_{KEY}_.

Parameters

key (str) – Configuration key.

Returns

Dictionary of configuration parameters for the specified key.

Examples

```
>>> fairly.get_config("fairly")
>>> {'orcid_client_id': 'id', 'orcid_client_secret': 'secret', ...}
```

`fairly.get_environment_config(key: str)` → Dict

Returns configuration parameters for the specified key from environmental variables.

Parameters

key (str) – Configuration key.

Returns

Dictionary of configuration parameters for the specified key.

Examples

```
>>> fairly.get_environment_config("fairly")
>>> {'orcid_client_id': 'id', ...}
```

`fairly.get_repositories()` → Dict

Returns recognized repositories.

Returns

Dictionary of the recognized repositories. Keys are repository identifiers (str), values are repository dictionaries (Dict).

Raises

- **ValueError** – If configuration is invalid.
- **AttributeError** – If a repository has no client id.
- **AttributeError** – If a repository has invalid client id.

Examples

```
>>> fairly.get_repositories()
>>> {'4tu': {'client_id': 'figshare', 'name': '4TU.ResearchData', 'url': 'https://
↳data.4tu.nl/', ...}, ...}
```

`fairly.get_repository(uid: str)` → Dict

Returns repository dictionary of the specified repository.

Parameters

uid (str) – Repository id or URL address.

Returns

Repository dictionary if a recognized repository, None otherwise.

Examples

```
>>> fairly.get_repository("4tu")
>>> {'id': '4tu', 'client_id': 'figshare', 'name': '4TU.ResearchData', 'url':
↳'https://data.4tu.nl/', ...}
```

```
>>> fairly.get_repository("5tu")
>>>
```

`fairly.init_dataset(path: str, template: str = 'default', create: bool = True)` → *LocalDataset*

Initializes a local dataset.

Parameters

- **path** (str) – Local path of the dataset.
- **template** – Template of the dataset (default = 'default').
- **create** – Set True to create the dataset directory if not exists (default = True)

Returns

Local dataset object

Raises

- **ValueError("Invalid path")** – If path is invalid.
- **NotADirectoryError** – If path is not a directory path.
- **ValueError("Operation not permitted")** – If path is an existing dataset path.
- **ValueError("Invalid template name")** – If template name is invalid.

`fairly.is_testing()` → bool

Returns unit testing state.

Returns

True if performing unit tests, False otherwise

`fairly.metadata_templates()` → List

Returns list of available metadata templates.

Returns

List of available metadata templates (str).

Examples

```
>>> fairly.metadata_templates()
>>> ['default', 'zenodo', 'figshare']
```

`fairly.notify(file: File, current_size: int, total_size: int = None, current_total_size: int = None)` → None

Displays file transfer information.

Parameters

- **file (File)** – File object.
- **current_size (int)** – Current size of the file.
- **total_size (int)** – Total size of the file (optional).
- **current_total_size (int)** – Current total size of the transfer operation (optional).

`fairly.store(id: str, path: str = None, notify: Callable = None, extract: bool = False)` → *LocalDataset*

Stores remote dataset locally

Parameters

- **id (str)** – Dataset identifier.
- **path (str)** – Local path to store the dataset (optional).
- **notify (Callable)** – Notification callback function.
- **extract (bool)** – Set True to extract dataset archives (default = False)

Returns

Local dataset object

INDICES AND TABLES

- genindex
- modindex
- search

PYTHON MODULE INDEX

f

- fairly, 56
- fairly.client, 39
 - fairly.client.djehuty, 33
 - fairly.client.figshare, 34
 - fairly.client.zenodo, 35
- fairly.dataset, 47
 - fairly.dataset.local, 43
 - fairly.dataset.remote, 45
- fairly.diff, 51
- fairly.file, 50
 - fairly.file.local, 48
 - fairly.file.remote, 50
- fairly.metadata, 52
- fairly.person, 53

Symbols

_account_datasets (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 _added (*fairly.diff.Diff* attribute), 51
 _attrs (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* attribute), 52
 _auto_refresh (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* attribute), 47
 _basis (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* attribute), 52
 _client (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* attribute), 45
 _datasets (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 _details (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 35
 _details (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* attribute), 45
 _excludes (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43
 _files (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* attribute), 47
 _id (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* attribute), 45
 _includes (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43
 _licenses (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 _manifest_path (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43
 _md5s (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43
 _metadata (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* attribute), 47
 _modified (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* attribute), 47
 _modified (*fairly.diff.Diff* attribute), 51
 _normalize (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* attribute), 52
 _path (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43
 _removed (*fairly.diff.Diff* attribute), 51
 _session (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 _yaml (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* attribute), 43

A

access_rights (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 35
 add() (*fairly.diff.Diff* method), 51
 added (*fairly.diff.Diff* property), 51
 append() (*fairly.person.PersonList* method), 55
 auto_refresh (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 47
 autocomplete() (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* method), 53
 autocomplete() (*fairly.person.Person* method), 54

C

categories (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* property), 34
 CHUNK_SIZE (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 CHUNK_SIZE (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile* attribute), 49
 Client (*class in fairly.client*), 39
 client (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 45
 client() (*in module fairly*), 56
 client_id (*fairly.client.Client* property), 39
 config (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39
 create_dataset() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 39
 created (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 47
 created (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 43
 created (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 45

D

Dataset (*class in fairly.dataset*), 47
 dataset() (*in module fairly*), 56
 delete_dataset() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 40
 delete_file() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 40
 Diff (*class in fairly.diff*), 51
 diff_files() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* method), 47
 diff_metadata() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* method), 47
 DjehutyClient (*class in fairly.client.djehuty*), 33
 doi (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 45
 download_file() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 40

E

excludes (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 43
 extend() (*fairly.person.PersonList* method), 55
 extension (*fairly.file.File* property), 50
 extract() (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile* method), 49

F

fairly
 module, 56
 fairly.client
 module, 39
 fairly.client.djehuty

- module, 33
 - fairly.client.figshare
 - module, 34
 - fairly.client.zenodo
 - module, 35
 - fairly.dataset
 - module, 47
 - fairly.dataset.local
 - module, 43
 - fairly.dataset.remote
 - module, 45
 - fairly.diff
 - module, 51
 - fairly.file
 - module, 50
 - fairly.file.local
 - module, 48
 - fairly.file.remote
 - module, 50
 - fairly.metadata
 - module, 52
 - fairly.person
 - module, 53
 - FigshareClient (*class in fairly.client.figshare*), 34
 - File (*class in fairly.file*), 50
 - file() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset method*), 47
 - files (*fairly.dataset.Dataset property*), 47
 - from_orcid_id() (*fairly.person.Person static method*), 54
 - fullpath (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile property*), 49
- G**
- get_account_datasets() (*fairly.client.Client method*), 40
 - get_archive_method() (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset method*), 44
 - get_archive_name() (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset method*), 44
 - get_categories() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient method*), 34
 - get_clients() (*in module fairly*), 57
 - get_communities() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient method*), 36
 - get_config() (*fairly.client.Client class method*), 40
 - get_config() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient class method*), 34
 - get_config() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient class method*), 36
 - get_config() (*in module fairly*), 57
 - get_config_parameters() (*fairly.client.Client class method*), 40
 - get_config_parameters() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient class method*), 34
 - get_config_parameters() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient class method*), 36
 - get_environment_config() (*in module fairly*), 57
 - get_file() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset method*), 47
 - get_files() (*fairly.client.Client method*), 41
 - get_files() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient method*), 35
 - get_files() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient method*), 37
 - get_files() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset method*), 47
 - get_funders() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient method*), 37
 - get_licenses() (*fairly.client.Client method*), 41
 - get_metadata() (*fairly.client.Client method*), 41
 - get_metadata() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset method*), 47
 - get_orcid_token() (*fairly.person.Person static method*), 54
 - get_persons() (*fairly.person.Person static method*), 55
 - get_remote_dataset() (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset method*), 44
 - get_repositories() (*in module fairly*), 58
 - get_repository() (*in module fairly*), 58
 - get_versions() (*fairly.client.Client method*), 42
 - get_versions() (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset method*), 46
 - grant_dois (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient attribute*), 37
- H**
- headers (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile property*), 50
- I**
- id (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset property*), 46
 - id (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile property*), 50
 - image_types (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient attribute*), 38
 - includes (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset property*), 44
 - init_dataset() (*in module fairly*), 58
 - insert() (*fairly.person.PersonList method*), 55
 - is_archive (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile property*), 49
 - is_modified (*fairly.dataset.Dataset property*), 48
 - is_modified (*fairly.metadata.Metadata property*), 53
 - is_simple (*fairly.file.File property*), 50

`is_testing()` (in module *fairly*), 59

K

`KEEP_ALIVE` (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 35

L

`licenses` (*fairly.client.Client* property), 42

`LocalDataset` (class in *fairly.dataset.local*), 43

`LocalFile` (class in *fairly.file.local*), 49

`LOCKED_SLEEP` (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* attribute), 34

`LOCKED_TRIES` (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* attribute), 34

M

`match()` (*fairly.file.File* method), 50

`match()` (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile* method), 49

`match()` (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* method), 50

`md5` (*fairly.file.File* property), 50

`md5` (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile* property), 50

`md5` (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* property), 50

`Metadata` (class in *fairly.metadata*), 52

`metadata` (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 48

`metadata_templates()` (in module *fairly*), 59

`modified` (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 48

`modified` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 44

`modified` (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 46

`modified` (*fairly.diff.Diff* property), 51

`modify()` (*fairly.diff.Diff* method), 52

module

fairly, 56

fairly.client, 39

fairly.client.djehuty, 33

fairly.client.figshare, 34

fairly.client.zenodo, 35

fairly.dataset, 47

fairly.dataset.local, 43

fairly.dataset.remote, 45

fairly.diff, 51

fairly.file, 50

fairly.file.local, 48

fairly.file.remote, 50

fairly.metadata, 52

fairly.person, 53

N

`name` (*fairly.file.File* property), 50

`name` (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* property), 50

`normalize()` (*fairly.client.Client* class method), 42

`normalize()` (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* class method), 53

`notify()` (in module *fairly*), 59

P

`PAGE_SIZE` (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* attribute), 34

`PAGE_SIZE` (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 35

`parse()` (*fairly.person.Person* class method), 55

`parse_id()` (*fairly.client.Client* class method), 42

`path` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 44

`path` (*fairly.file.File* property), 50

`Person` (class in *fairly.person*), 54

`PersonList` (class in *fairly.person*), 55

`print()` (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* method), 53

`publication_types` (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 38

`pull()` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

`push()` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

R

`rebase()` (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* method), 53

`record_type_lookup` (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* attribute), 35

`record_types` (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* attribute), 35

`record_types` (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 38

`REGEXP_DOI` (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* attribute), 53

`REGEXP_EMAIL` (*fairly.person.Person* attribute), 54

`REGEXP_ORCID_ID` (*fairly.person.Person* attribute), 54

`REGEXP_URL` (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39

`REGEXP_UUID` (*fairly.client.djehuty.DjehutyClient* attribute), 33

`relations` (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* attribute), 38

`remote_datasets` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 44

`RemoteDataset` (class in *fairly.dataset.remote*), 45

`RemoteFile` (class in *fairly.file.remote*), 50

`remove()` (*fairly.diff.Diff* method), 52

`removed` (*fairly.diff.Diff* property), 52

`repository_id` (*fairly.client.Client* property), 42

`reproduce()` (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* method), 48

`reproduce()` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

`reproduce()` (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* method), 46

`REQUEST_FORMAT` (*fairly.client.Client* attribute), 39

S

`save()` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

`save_config()` (*fairly.client.Client* method), 42

`save_files()` (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

save_metadata() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 42
 save_metadata() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* method), 35
 save_metadata() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* method), 38
 save_metadata() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* method), 48
 serialize() (*fairly.metadata.Metadata* method), 53
 serialize() (*fairly.person.Person* method), 55
 set_metadata() (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* method), 48
 set_remote_dataset()
 (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44
 size (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 48
 size (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 44
 size (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 46
 size (*fairly.file.File* property), 51
 size (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* property), 50
 status (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 46
 store() (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* method), 46
 store() (*in module fairly*), 59
 supports_folder() (*fairly.client.Client* class method), 42
 supports_folder() (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* class method), 35
 supports_folder() (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* class method), 38
 synchronize() (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44

T

template (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* property), 44
 title (*fairly.dataset.Dataset* property), 48
 title (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 46
 type (*fairly.file.File* property), 51
 type (*fairly.file.local.LocalFile* property), 50
 type (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* property), 50

U

upload() (*fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset* method), 44
 upload_file() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 42
 url (*fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset* property), 47
 url (*fairly.file.remote.RemoteFile* property), 50

V

validate_metadata() (*fairly.client.Client* method), 42
 validate_metadata()
 (*fairly.client.figshare.FigshareClient* method), 35
 validate_metadata()
 (*fairly.client.zenodo.ZenodoClient* method), 38

Z

ZenodoClient (*class in fairly.client.zenodo*), 35